

Interdisciplinary Knowledge Base on Digital Democracy

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Abstract

A thematic knowledge base that defines the main elements of digital democracy, namely a) digital deliberation in the digital public sphere, b) online participation, c) open governance, d) digital activism, e) E-voting and enabling technologies, alongside best practices in digital democracy and its dimensions, global trends, problems, and risks that shape the realities and prospects for digital democracy.

Benefits

- To document and understand the state-of-the-art of how digital democracy has been theorised and analysed.
- To better understand how various detailed aspects of digital democracy have been analysed and theorized
- To better understand the risks that digital democracy is facing
- To learn from best practices in digital democracy research

Why is it important?

Digital society faces a wide range of challenges today: fake news and misinformation, foreign information manipulation and interference, digital authoritarianism, big-tech monopolies, digital exclusion, echo chambers, algorithmic bias, and an increasingly emotional, post-truth culture. In this context, INNOVADE's mission to understand and strengthen digital democracy is more urgent than ever.

Online resource

The Interdisciplinary Knowledge Base on Digital Democracy is available for free online:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17079016>

Involved

Stakeholders

Researchers

Policymakers & policy-facing CSOs, Public Administration

Quote

If we want to properly shield digital democracy, then we need to know what it is that we want to defend. The questions arise: What is democracy? What is digital democracy? Understanding and advancing digital democracy requires a good understanding of what democracy and digital democracy are all about.

Prof. Christian Fuchs, leader of the Paderborn University-research team

